

ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE ESTIMATION OF BISOPROLOL FUMARATE: A TECHNICAL REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Bisoprolol fumarate is a drug mainly used for the long-term treatment of high blood pressure. It works by reducing the heart rate and lowering the workload on the heart, which helps in controlling blood pressure with fewer breathing-related side effects. This review focuses on different analytical methods such as UV-Visible Spectroscopy, HPLC, and HPTLC used for estimation of Bisoprolol fumarate in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms. It also highlights the importance of method validation as per ICH guidelines to ensure the quality, safety, and effectiveness of the drug.

KEYWORDS: Bisoprolol fumarate, Hypertension, RP HPLC, UV Spectroscopy, Method validation, Stability indicator.

INTRODUCTION

Blood pressure refers to the force exerted by circulating blood on the walls of the arteries. It normally fluctuates throughout the day depending on physical activity, stress, and other body functions. However, when blood pressure remains consistently higher than normal for a prolonged period, the condition is known as hypertension. An optimal blood pressure reading is generally considered to be below 120 mm hg for systolic pressure and below 80 mm hg for diastolic pressure (120/80 mm hg) persistent high blood pressure can increase the risk of serious health problems

including heart disease and stroke. In many cases, hypertension does not show obvious symptoms, which makes it difficult to detect early. However, extremely high blood pressure may lead to warning signs such as intense headaches, visual disturbance, and chest discomfort.^[1,2]

Hypertension is a medical condition characterized by a continuous increase in blood pressure levels above 140/90 mm/hg. Blood pressure is considered normal or optimal when the systolic pressure is below 120 mm/hg and the diastolic pressure is below 80 mm/hg.

Introduction of bisoprolol fumarate

Bisoprolol fumarate is classified as a selective β_1 -adrenergic receptor antagonist that mainly acts on the heart. It is commonly prescribed for the treatment of several cardiovascular conditions, especially congestive heart failure. Since this drug primarily blocks β_1 receptors, its effects are mostly limited to cardiac tissues. This selectivity helps reduce the likelihood of β_2 receptor inhibition, which may otherwise lead to unwanted effects in other body systems.^[4]

Bisoprolol is FDA-approved for the management of hypertension. Clinicians must recognize that according to ACC/AHA guidelines, bisoprolol or other beta blockers are not the first-line treatment for hypertension unless the patient has ischemic heart disease or HFrEF.^[5]

Bisoprolol is used in the treatment plan for compensated heart failure. According to 2022 AHA/ACC/HFSA guidelines, specific beta-blockers (bisoprolol, metoprolol succinate, and carvedilol) are included in guideline-directed medical therapy (GDMT) for heart failure with reduced ejection fraction (HFrEF). Bisoprolol is recommended to reduce mortality and hospitalizations in patients with HFrEF.^[6]

Selective β_1 -adrenergic blocking agents are generally regarded as the preferred initial therapy for patients with chronic stable angina.

The 2020 practice guidelines published by the International Society of Hypertension recommend the use of cardioselective β -blockers, including bisoprolol, in individuals with coronary artery disease, with or without the addition of calcium channel blockers.^[7]

Chemically, bisoprolol fumarate is a synthetic phenoxy propanolamine derivative with the IUPAC name (RS)-1-[4-[(2-isopropoxyethoxy) methyl] phenoxy]-3-(isopropyl amino)

propan-2-ol fumarate. It appearing as a white to almost white crystalline powder and freely soluble in water and methanol. Bisoprolol fumarate has the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{31}NO_4 \cdot C_4H_4O_4$ and a molecular weight of approximately 766.96 g/mol. The drug exhibits moderate lipophilicity with a log P value of about 1.9 and a pKa of approximately 9.5, contributing to its good oral absorption and high bioavailability.^[8]

Mechanism of action

Bisoprolol is a selective β_1 -adrenergic receptor antagonist that mainly acts on the heart. By blocking β_1 -receptors, it reduces heart rate, myocardial contractility, and cardiac output. This action decreases cardiac workload and oxygen demand, resulting in antihypertensive and cardioprotective effects.

Bisoprolol also lower blood pressure by decreasing the release of renin from the kidneys. In addition, it may reduce sympathetic nervous system activity from the brain. These effects help to decrease both heart rate and blood pressure, contributing to its antihypertensive action.^[9]

Fig. 1: Chemical structure of Bisoprolol.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bisoprolol Fumarate Official Methods

No.	Title	Description	Reference No.
1	Bisoprolol fumarate (IP-2018)	Column: stainless steel column Column size: (12.5cm x 4.6 mm, packed with octyl silane bonded to porous silica 5 μ m – particle size) Wavelength: 273 nm Solvent: water: acetonitrile (65:35v/v) Flow rate: 1 ml min ⁻¹ Injection volume: 10 μ l	[10]
	Bisoprolol fumarate (USP-2015)	Column: LiChrospher 7 column (octa silane C ₈ column) Column size: (12.5cm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m – particle size) Wavelength: 273 nm	[11]

		Solvent: water: acetonitrile (65:35v/v) Flow rate: 1 ml min ⁻¹ Injection volume: 10 µl	
3	Bisoprolol fumarate (BP-2009)	Column: C ₁₈ column Column size: (0.25m × 4.6mm, packed with octyl silane 5µm – particle size) Wavelength: 225 nm Solvent: acetonitrile: water (20:80v/v) Flow rate: 1 ml min ⁻¹ Injection volume: 10 µl	[12]

3.1.1 Bisoprolol Fumarate Reported Methods

No.	Title	Method	Description	Reference No.
1	Bisoprolol fumarate	Stability RP indicating HPLC	Column: Oyster ODS3 (150mm x 4.6 mm, 5 µm) Mobile phase: orthophosphoric acid: methanol: acetonitrile (42:29:29, v/v/v) Wavelength: 230 nm Flow rate: 1.0 ml min ⁻¹ Range: BIS: 60.08– 140.19µg ml ⁻¹ AML: 59.73–139.37 µg ml ⁻¹ Retention time: BIS: 4.4 min, AML: 6.4 min	[13]
2	Bisoprolol fumarate	HPLC	Column: Zorbax Rx C ₈ (250mm×4.6mm, 5µm) Mobile phase: Methanol: perchloric acid (55:45v/v) Flow rate: 1ml min ⁻¹ Wavelength: 214nm Range: Bisoprolol: 20–200ug ml ⁻¹ Enalapril: 20–200 ug ml ⁻¹ Retention time: BIS: 4.6 min, ENL: 5.18 min	[14]
3	Bisoprolol fumarate	RP-HPLC	Column: (C ₁₈) Inertsil ODS 3V column (150 x 4.6mm,5µm) Mobile phase: buffer: methanol: (20:80 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml min ⁻¹ Wavelength: 231nm Range: Bisoprolol Fumarate: 5-25µg ml ⁻¹ Cilnidipine: 10-50µg ml ⁻¹ Retention time: BIS: 2.84 min, CIL: 1.51 min	[15]
4	Bisoprolol	RP-HPLC	Column: Column C ₁₈ (250 mm× 4.6	[16]

	fumarate		mm) Mobile phase: Methanol: Water (65:35 v/v) Wavelength: 230 nm Range: 5-25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Flow rate: 0.1 ml min^{-1} Retention time: AML: 3.49 min, BIS: 6.52 min	
5	Bisoprolol fumarate	UV	Model: shimadzu1800uv/VIS Solvent: methanol:water (80:20v/v) Wavelength: 200-400 nm Range: BIS: 5- 15 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ CIL:10-30 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	[17]
6	Bisoprolol fumarate	HPLC	HPLC: in human plasma Column: C ₁₈ reverse-phase column (Inertsil, 4 mm, 150 × 4.6 mm) Mobile phase: methanol-water (70:30v/v) Flow rate: 1.2 ml min^{-1} Range: 10–2000 mg ml ⁻¹ Retention time: 4.79 min	[18]
7	Bisoprolol fumarate	UV	Model: shimadzu1800 uv/VIS Solvent: water Wavelength : 200-400 nm Range: BIS: 5-25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$	[19]
8	Bisoprolol fumarate	RP-HPLC	Column : Shiseido – C ₁₈ (250mm×4.6mm, 5 μm) Mobile phase: Phosphate buffer (pH3.5): Methanol (60:40v/v) Flow rate: 1.0ml min^{-1} Wavelength: 225 nm Range: CIL:10-30 $\mu\text{ ml}^{-1}$ BIS:5-15 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Retention time: CIL: 4.053 min, BIS :5.730 min	[20]
9	Bisoprolol fumarate	UV	Column: C ₁₈ (5 μm , 4.6mm×250 mm) Mobile phase: methanol: phosphate buffer solution (65:35 v/v) Flow rate: 1.0 ml min^{-1} Wavelength: 225 nm Range: BIS: 5-25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Retention time: 2.8 min	[21]

CONCLUSION

This review concludes that bisoprolol fumarate is an effective drug for the treatment of hypertension and heart-related disorders. It acts by reducing heart rate and decreasing cardiac

workload. Various analytical methods such as UV spectroscopy, HPLC, and RP-HPLC are useful for its estimation in pharmaceutical dosage forms. Method validation according to guidelines ensures accuracy and reliability of results. Hence, proper analysis of bisoprolol fumarate is essential for maintaining drug quality.

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